

Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocycles : Facile Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazines and Pyrazolo[3',4' : 4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazines

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In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis of condensed bridgehead nitrogen heterocyclic systems, we report herein the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 6-aryl-3-(α -naphthyl)-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazines (2), 3-(α -naphthyl)-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-one (3) and 8-aryl-3-(α -naphthyl)-2,3,7,8-tetrahydro-4*H*,8*aH*-pyrazolo[3',4' : 4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazines (5) starting from 6-(α -naphthyl)-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-*s*-tetrazin-3(2*H*)-thione (1).

6-(α -Naphthyl)-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-*s*-tetrazin-3(2*H*)-thione (1) (obtained by the reaction of α -naphthaldehyde with thiocarbohydrazide following the method of Lamon¹) on condensation with α -halogenoketones and chloroacetic acid furnished 6-aryl-3-(α -naphthyl)-2,3-dihydro-4*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine hydrohalides (2) and 3-(α -naphthyl)-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-one (3)

respectively. The structures of 2 and 3 were supported by their ir and nmr spectral data. The absence and presence of ir absorption at 1660–1735 cm⁻¹ (C=O) in case of 2 and 3 respectively, support the cyclic structures. 7-Arylidene-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4*H*-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-ones (4) were prepared by the following two routes. In the first route, the thiazolidinone (3) was condensed with aldehydes, while in the second route, these were obtained directly by heating 1 with ethyl chloroacetate and aldehydes in presence of pyridine and piperidine. Structures of 4 were supported by their ir spectra. The parent thiazolidinone (3) absorbed at 1730 cm⁻¹ (>N—C=O) but the exocyclic double bond at 7-position being in conjugation with carbonyl group at 6-position produced a bathochromic shift² in the carbonyl absorption of 4. The band appeared at 1705 cm⁻¹ in 4 (Ar=*p*-MeO-C₆H₄-).

Condensation of 4 with hydrazine hydrate/2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine yielded in one step the cyclised products 8-aryl-3-(α -naphthyl)-2,3,7,8-tetrahydro-4H, 8aH-pyrazolo[3',4':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazines (5). Lack of ir absorption in the spectra of 5 at 1690–1710 cm^{-1} suggests the cyclic structures. Their structures were supported by the pmr spectral data.

Compounds 2a ($R_1 = p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$ -), 2b ($R_1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $(\text{OCH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3$ -), 3,5a-2 ($R = \text{H}$, $\text{Ar} = p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$ -) and 5b-3 ($R = 2,4\text{-(NO}_2)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3$ -, $\text{Ar} = p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$ -) were evaluated for antimicrobial activity against the gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and fungus *Candida albicans* by neat samples and serial plate dilution method³.

The minimum inhibitory concentration of the compounds 5a, 3 and 5b against *S. aureus* were found to be 250, 125 and 62.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively. The compounds 2a and 2b were found to be active against *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*.

Experimental

Tlc was run on silica gel plates using acetone-benzene (1 : 3) as irrigant. Melting points are uncorrected. Ir and pmr (downfield from TMS) spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 722B and Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instruments, respectively.

6-(α -Naphthyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-s-tetrazin-3(2H)thione (1): It was prepared in 62% yield by the reaction of α -naphthaldehyde with thiocarbohydrazide according to the reported method¹, (62%), m.p. 223° (Found; N, 23.12; S, 12.89. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires; N, 22.95; S, 13.11%); ν_{max} 730, 770, 1120, 1515, 1610, 3180 and 3350 cm^{-1} .

3-(α -Naphthyl)-6-p-chlorophenyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-tetrazine hydrobromide (2a; $R = p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$ -): A mixture of 1 (1.22 g, 0.005 mol) and p-bromophenacyl bromide (1.39 g, 0.005 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) and DMF (4 ml), was refluxed for 0.5 h on a steam-bath. The mixture

Scheme 1

was then cooled, poured into water, and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol as brown crystals (1.8 g, 70%), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 47.37; H, 3.13; N, 10.81; S, 6.64. $C_{20}H_{16}N_4SBr_2$ requires: C, 47.61; H, 3.17; N, 11.11 and S, 6.34%); ν_{max} 770, 790, 830, 1 520, 1 580, 1 600, 3 050 and 3 275 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.25 (1H, s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 3.70 (1H, s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 4.50 (1H, s, N^+H), 6.90 (1H, s, C_7-H), 7.4–8.9 (11H, m, ArH) and 9.0 (1H, s, H-3)

Other thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazines (2) prepared similarly were 2b (obtained from 1 and phenacyl chloride), (78%), m.p. 146° (Found: N, 15.11; S, 8.22. $C_{20}H_{17}N_4S$ requires: N, 14.71; S, 8.40); 2c (obtained from 1 and *p*- $C_6H_4-C_6H_4-COCH_2Br$), (45%), m.p. 156° (Found: N, 10.86; S, 6.57. $C_{26}H_{21}N_4SBr$ requires: N, 11.17; S, 6.38%).

3-(α -Naphthyl)-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-thiazolo-[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-one (3): A mixture of 1 (2.44 g, 0.01 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.95 g, 0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) in a mixture of anhydrous ethanol (60 ml) and DMF (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 h, then concentrated, cooled and poured into water. The solid thus obtained was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as greenish yellow crystals (1.6 g, 56%), m.p. 163° (Found: C, 59.63; H, 4.39; N, 20.06; S, 10.97. $C_{14}H_{12}N_4SO$ requires: C, 59.15; H, 4.22; N, 19.71; S, 11.26%); ν_{max} 742, 770, 800, 1 230, 1 400, 1 510, 1 600, 1 730 and 3 350 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 3.8 (2H, s, CH_2CO), 4.0 (1H, s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 4.70 (1H, s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 7.4–8.9 (7H, m, ArH) and 9.1 (1H, s, H-3).

3-(α -Naphthyl)-7-(*p*-methoxybenzylidene)-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-one (4a, $Ar=p-MeO-C_6H_4$). Method (a): A mixture of 3 (2.84 g, 0.01 mol), *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde (1.36 g, 0.01 mol), fused sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) and glacial acetic acid (40 ml) was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled and poured into cold water. The yellow solid thus separated, was washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow crystals, (2.56 g, 60%), m.p. 206° (Found: N, 14.24; S, 8.21. $C_{22}H_{18}N_4SO_2$ requires: N, 13.93; S, 7.96%); ν_{max} 752, 778, 830, 1 120, 1 285, 1 515, 1 620, 1 705, 3 040, 3 280 and 3 420 cm^{-1} .

A similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of 3-(α -naphthyl)-7-benzylidene-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-one (4b, $Ar=C_6H_5$) from 3 and benzaldehyde, (65%), m.p. 218° (Found: S, 8.27; N, 15.47. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4OS$ requires: S, 8.62; N, 15.09%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-7-(*p*-chlorobenzylidene)-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-one (4c, $Ar=p-ClC_6H_4$) from 3 and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, (65%), m.p. 196° (Found: S, 8.02; N, 13.38. $C_{21}H_{15}N_4OSCl$ requires: S, 7.87; N, 13.77%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-7-(3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-one (4d, $Ar=3,4(MeO)_2-C_6H_3$) from 3 and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde, (68%), m.p. 183°

(Found: S, 8.22; N, 14.35. $C_{28}H_{20}N_4O_3S$ requires: S, 7.96; N, 13.93%); and 3-(α -naphthyl)-7-*p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene)-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazin-6-one (4e, $Ar=p-(CH_3)_2N-C_6H_4$) from 3 and *p*- $(CH_3)_2NC_6H_4CHO$, (65%), m.p. 238° (Found: S, 7.46; N, 16.49. $C_{28}H_{21}N_5OS$ requires: S, 7.71; N, 16.86%).

Method (b): A mixture of 1 (1.22 g, 0.005 mol), ethyl chloroacetate (0.61 g, 0.005 mol) and pyridine (0.45 ml) in a mixture of anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) and DMF (5 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 4 h. *p*-Methoxybenzaldehyde (0.68 g, 0.005 mol) and piperidine (0.35 ml) were then added and the reaction mixture was refluxed further for 4 h. It was then cooled, poured into cold water and the resulting yellow solid was washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow crystals (4a; 1.28 g, 60%), m.p. and m.m.p. 206°.

3-(α -Naphthyl)-7-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-8-(*p*-anisyl)-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-4H-pyrazolo[3',4':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5b-1): A mixture of 4a (2.01 g, 0.005 mol), 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.99 g, 0.005 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.41 g, 0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. It was then cooled, poured into water and the resulting orange solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol as orange crystals (1.8 g, 62%), m.p. 218° (Found: C, 57.48; H, 3.49; N, 18.87; S, 5.78. $C_{28}H_{22}N_8O_5S$ requires: C, 57.73; H, 3.78; N, 19.24; S, 5.49%); ν_{max} 745, 770, 825, 835, 870, 1 145, 1 310, 1 520, 1 600, 1 625, 3 060, 3 170 and 3 400 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.6 (2H, brs, NH exchangeable with D_2O), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-8a), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-8), 7.5–9.20 (14H, m, ArH) and 9.10 (1H, s, H-3).

A similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of 3-(α -naphthyl)-8-phenyl-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-4H-pyrazolo[3',4':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5a-1; R=H, $Ar=C_6H_5$) from 4b and hydrazine, (55%), m.p. 162° (Found: S, 7.86; N, 21.24. $C_{21}H_{18}N_6S$ requires: S, 8.29; N, 21.76%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-8-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-4H-pyrazolo[3',4':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5a-2; R=H, $Ar=p-ClC_6H_4$) from 4c and hydrazine, (62%), m.p. 232° (Found: S, 7.19; N, 20.23. $C_{21}H_{17}N_6S$ requires: S, 7.60; N, 19.97%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-8-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-4H-pyrazolo[3',4':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5a-3; R=H, $Ar=3,4-(OCH_3)_2C_6H_3$) from 4 and hydrazine, (65%), m.p. 183° (Found: S, 7.52; N, 18.56. $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_6S$ requires: S, 7.17; N, 18.83%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-8-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-4H-pyrazolo[3',4':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5a-4; R=H, $Ar=p-Me_2NC_6H_4$) from 4e and hydrazine, (66%), m.p. 178° (Found: S, 7.21; N, 23.01. $C_{28}H_{23}N_7S$ requires: S, 7.45; N, 22.84%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-7-2,4-dinitrophenyl-8-phenyl-2,3,8,8a-tetrahydro-4H-pyrazolo[3',4':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5b-2; R=2,4-(NO_2) $_2C_6H_3$, $Ar=C_6H_5$) from 4b and 2,4-dinitro-

phenylhydrazine, (65%), m.p. 165° (Found : S, 5.58 ; N, 19.76. $C_{27}H_{20}O_4N_8S$ requires : S, 5.79 ; N, 20.28%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-7-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-8-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2,3,8*a*-tetrahydro-4*H*-pyrazolo[3',4' : 4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5b-3 ; R=2,4-(NO₂)₂C₆H₃-, Ar=*p*-ClC₆H₄-) from 4c and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, (60%), m.p. 236° (Found : S, 5.92 ; N, 18.80. $C_{27}H_{18}O_4N_8S$ requires : S, 5.45 ; N, 19.09%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-7-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-8-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-2,3,8*a*-tetrahydro-4*H*-pyrazolo[3',4' : 4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5b-4 ; R=2,4-(NO₂)₂C₆H₃-, Ar=3,4-(OCH₃)₂C₆H₃-) from 4d and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, (62%), m.p. 145° (Found : S, 4.98 ; N, 18.72. $C_{29}H_{24}O_6N_8S$ requires : N, 18.30 ; S, 5.22%); 3-(α -naphthyl)-7-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-8-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-2,3,8*a*-tetrahydro-4*H*-pyrazolo[3',4' : 4,5]thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-tetrazine (5b-5 ; R=2,4-(NO₂)₂C₆H₃-, Ar=*p*-Me₂NC₆H₄-) from 4e and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, (68%), m.p. 183°

(Found : S, 5.64 ; N, 21.55. $C_{29}H_{24}N_8O_4S$ requires : S, 5.37 ; N, 21.17%).

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